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Research

Study on the Development of Sino-Thai Tourism Trade Services

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Abstract: The full text is based on tourism services trade issues between China and Thailand. First, through a lot of data to illustrate the development of tourism between the two countries before, including the development of the history and development of the status quo. Secondly, China and Thailand noted in the tourism trade in services in the problems, "zero fare" issue, as well as China and Thailand tourism trade deficit problem exists mainly on trade in services in the Thai tourism market today. In response to these problems, the author lists the measures taken by the two governments, and put forward their own ideas. Finally, the future of China and Thailand tourism service trade development and make prospects.

Keywords: Travel ; Service Trade; Thailand;

1. Introduction

1.1 current situation of China's tourism

In recent years, China's tourism industry has shown a vigorous development trend. In 2018, the number of inbound tourists reached 141.2 million, an increase of 5.56 percentage points compared with 133.76million in 2010. From 2010 to 2018, the number of inbound tourists has been hovering around 128-141 million, with relatively small fluctuation. Between 2010 and 2018, only in 2013 and 2014 the number of inbound tourists is less than 130 million (see Table 1-1 for details).

Table 1-1 statistics of inbound tourists from 2010 to 2018 (million person-time) (data source: Official Website of the National Bureau of statistics of the people's Republic of China)

Year	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018
Inbound tourists number	133.76	135.42	132.4	129.07	128.49	133.82	138.44	139.48	141.2

The following table shows the statistics of the number of Thai tourists who visited China from 2004 to 2018. Comparing data in Table 1 and table 2, it is not difficult to find that the change trend of the two data is basically the same. From 2004 to 2007, the number of tourists from Thailand to China increased year by year, but from 2007 to 2011, it decreased for four consecutive years. Although it rebounded in 2012 and 2013, the range was relatively small. In 2014, the number of tourists from Thailand to China fell again (see table 1-2 for details).

Table 1-2 statistics of Thai tourists to China from 2004 to 2018 (data source: Official Website of the National Bureau of statistics of the people's Republic of China)

Year	Number of people (thousands)	Year-on-year growth	Year	Number of people (thousands)	Year-on-year growth
2004	464.2		2012	647.6	1.74
2005	586.267	26.3	2013	651.7	0.63
2006	591.956	0.97	2014	613.1	-5.92
2007	611.615	3.32	2015	633.4	3.31
2008	554.275	-9.38	2016	701.26	10.71
2009	541.8	-2.25	2017	741.3	5.71
2010	635.5	17.29	2018	730.12	-1.51
2011	608	-4.33			

1.2 tourism status in Thailand

Thanks to the support of the Thai government, in recent years, Thailand's tourism industry has become more and more prosperous, attracting more and more foreign tourists to Thailand. Since 2004, the number of foreign tourists to Thailand has been increasing gradually, and the income of tourism industry has been rising at the same time (see table 1-3 for details).

Table 1-3 number of foreign tourists and tourism income to Thailand in 2004-2012 (data source: Tourism Authority of Thailand (2013))

Year	Number of people (million)	Year on year growth in number (%)	Tourism revenue (100 million baht)	Tourism revenue growth year on year (%)
2004	11.65	16.46	384.36	24.28
2005	11.52	-1.51	367.38	-4.42
2006	13.82	17	482.3	31.29
2007	14.46	4.65	547.78	13.57
2008	14.53	0.83	574.52	4.88
2009	14.15	-2.98	510.25	-11.19
2010	15.93	12.63	592.79	16.18
2011	19.23	19.84	776.21	23.92
2012	22.3	15.96	767.47	-1.13
2013	26.55	19.06	12130.78	22.89
2014	24.78	-6.67	11750.35	-3.14
2015	29.90	20.66	14532.61	23.68
2016	32.57	8.93	16378.12	12.7
2017	35.43	7.46	18199.71	11.12
2018	38.28	7.54	20075.13	9.63

Compared with the change of the number of foreign tourists to Thailand, the change range of Thailand's tourism income is larger (see Figure 1-4 for details).

Figure 1-4 year on year growth rate of number of tourists to Thailand and tourism revenue in Thailand from 2004 to 2018

The number of Chinese tourists to Thailand is basically increasing. Although in 2005 and 2007-2009, the number of Chinese tourists to Thailand shows a downward trend compared with the previous year, compared with the growth rate in other years, the decline was relatively slow (see table 1-5 for details). From 2009 to 2018, it has been on the rise.

Table 1-5 statistics of tourists to Thailand from 2004 to 2018 (data source: China Tourism Statistics Bulletin (2004-2013) issued by China National Tourism Administration)

Year	Number of people (million)	Year on year growth in number (%)	Year	Number of people (million)	Year on year growth in number (%)
2004	68.21		2012	224.48	47.4
2005	59.55	-12.7	2013	401.03	78.7
2006	76.69	28.8	2014	460.86	14.92
2007	71.69	-6.5	2015	793.38	72.15
2008	62.39	-13	2016	877.16	10.56
2009	62.19	-0.3	2017	963.33	9.82
2010	101.46	63.1	2018	1035.21	7.44
2011	152.26	50.1			

2 problems in China and Thailand tourism service trade

2.1 "zero group fee"

As an overseas market that can be developed earlier in China's outbound tourism market, the number of Chinese tourists to Thailand has always been high, but in the process of rapid development of tourism trade between China and Thailand, there are "zero group fee" tourism groups, even "negative group fee" tourism groups. And it shows a deteriorating trend. This problem directly interferes with the healthy tourism trade between the two countries. If it is not solved, it is likely to affect the traditional friendly relations between the two countries in the future.

The so-called "zero group fee" refers to the fact that some travel agencies in China, in order to attract more tourists, do not hesitate to charge customers only for round-trip air tickets, but not other fees. At this time, the other travel agency will try to "buy a group" for more tourists. In order to make profits, the tour guide who provides services for the group will arrange tourists to do a lot of shopping, which makes the service quality of the travel agency decline and directly damages the interests of Chinese tourists. Figure 2-1 shows the reception mode of "zero group fee" tour guide.

If the issue of "zero group fee" is not stopped, it will have a serious negative impact on China and Thailand.

(1) For Thailand

① Endangering the development of Thai Travel agencies. "Zero group fee" means to adopt a low-cost charging mode. If travel agencies in Thailand want to make profits, they can only choose to increase shopping and self-expense, which directly changes the original intention of tourists to Thailand. With the rise of social self-Media, there are more and more ways for tourists to complain and media to break news, and either way will directly affect the reputation of travel

agencies, thus making their operation in hidden dangers. In the vicious circle, the travel agencies are not expanded.

② Damaging the image of tourist destination. At present, with the development of science and technology and the diversity of media, the news media's report on the problem of "zero group fee" and the publicity of tourists will seriously damage the image of the tourist destination. It will directly affect the potential Chinese tourists who are going to Thailand for tourism in the future. Intuitively, it will directly affect the tourism revenue of Thailand. On the other hand, by the end of 2018, 93 countries and regions, except Hong Kong and Macao, have become outbound tourism destinations of Chinese citizens. According to the order of the formal launch of the market, 89 countries are: Thailand, Singapore, etc. This shows that the choice of outbound travel for mainland Chinese citizens is more diversified. If the problem of "zero group fee" is not properly solved, then Thailand will inevitably have a situation of reduced market share in China.

(2) For China

① Damaging personal interests of tourists directly.

"Zero group fee" means low price, but it is undoubtedly a "trap" for tourists. In order to make profits, travel agencies, while reducing services, take forced means to require tourists to consume. For tourists who refuse to consume, and even worse, they will take certain violent means. In addition, tour guides often collude with travel souvenirs and other businesses to cheat tourists and make tourists spend meaninglessly for many times. This mode is not in line with the original intention of tourists' outbound travel.

② Damaging the traditional friendship between the two countries

Outbound tourism is comparable to diplomatic activities. If the tourism service trade between the two countries develops smoothly, it will certainly be conducive to strengthening the bilateral relations. In addition to boosting GDP growth and increasing employment, the two peoples can also reach friendship. The direct contact of Chinese tourists directly affects the impression of Chinese people on Thailand. Through the oral propaganda of tourists, it will affect the impression of Chinese people on Thailand. Therefore, the issue of "zero group fee" will directly affect the maintenance of friendly relations between the two countries.

2.2 Imbalance of tourism service trade between the two countries

The imbalance of tourism service trade between China and Thailand has a long history. China has been in a deficit position in the tourism service trade between China and Thailand. In recent years, the deficit has expanded (see table 2-2 for details).

Table 2-2 Inbound tourism situation of China's outbound tourism destination countries and major tourist source countries

Year	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018
Rank 1	7	5	4	2	1	1	1	1
Rank 2	14	13	13	13	13	13	13	13

According to the above table, it is not difficult to find that from 2011 to 2018, Thailand has always occupied the top 10 countries of outbound tourism destinations of Chinese citizens, but among the foreign tourists to China, the number of Thai tourists is always ranked outside the top 10. Combined with table 1-2 and table 1-5, the number of Chinese tourists to Thailand is far larger than that of Thai tourists to China, and the deficit has increased dramatically in recent years.

3 Solutions to the problems in China Thailand tourism service trade

3.1 For the problem of "mission zero"

(1) Measures taken by the Thai government

With regard to the phenomenon of "zero group fee", the Thai government has taken a series of tough measures. Thailand tourism administration has signed contracts with 9 travel agencies in China, making them the commanding heights in the market and gradually letting the tourism market get rid of the vicious circle. Set up a special supervision organization to check the group behavior of travel agencies in real time. In case of any non-compliance with the regulations of Thailand tourism administration, the travel agencies will be severely punished. Tourists can also complain about dissatisfied travel agencies according to relevant laws, and Thailand tourism bureau can impose heavy punishment on the travel agencies after verification. In order to facilitate Chinese tourists, the Thai government has also set up a "Chinese complaint center". Thailand tourism administration also launched three special fee relief programs for Chinese tourists.

(2) The author's opinion

① Thailand's tourism sector should stepped up supervision. Relevant tourism departments in Thailand should strengthen the supervision of tourism projects set up by travel agencies, and can selectively send special personnel to follow the tour group to supervise its behavior, and

vigorously punish illegal behaviors. They can also set up a special position to inquire from tourists. Once there is "zero group fee", it will be reported to the relevant authorities immediately.

② Thai officials should stepped up penalties. For "zero group fee" travel agencies, fines can not solve the problem from the source. For travel agencies committing for the first-time, Thai authorities can require them to close down for a certain period of time for rectification. For travel agencies with "zero group fee" for many times, they will directly ban the business qualification of the travel group and prohibit the relevant responsible persons of the enterprise from continuing to engage in tourism related businesses.

③ Developing tourism strategy for Chinese tourists. The Thai government and relevant functional departments in charge of inbound tourism should formulate special tourism development strategies for Chinese tourists and develop new tourism projects for Chinese tourists, especially the majority of current Chinese tourists choose to travel with groups, so they can more open up China's self-service tourism market. In order to better maintain the honor and international image of Thailand, the Thai government should urge Thai travel agencies to adjust some tourism projects, and remove the old, vulgar, unhealthy or improper tourism projects. Develop more tourism projects and products to meet the increasingly diversified tourism needs of Chinese tourists. In addition, Chinese road signs can be added, and Chinese Consultation stations can be set up in tourist attractions with large flow of people to facilitate tourists' inquiries.

3.2 imbalance of tourism service trade between the two countries

(1) Improve the competitiveness of China's tourism industry

In order to improve the competitiveness of China's tourism industry, we must strengthen the construction of tourism infrastructure, optimize the industrial structure, and strengthen the formulation of tourism laws and regulations. In 2013, Premier Li Keqiang proposed at the 16th China ASEAN (10 + 1) leaders' meeting to strengthen connectivity construction plan, determine and launch landmark cooperation projects as soon as possible, and jointly promote the construction of "Pan Asian Railway". The project can accelerate the integration of China ASEAN Free Trade Area. In addition, the establishment of the AIIB is conducive to promoting the construction of regional economic integration in Asia, promoting investment in infrastructure in Asia and promoting economic growth in Asia. It also laid a solid foundation for the tourism

service trade between China and Thailand. On this basis, China should improve the construction of tourism infrastructure and optimize the structure of tourism industry. China should also strengthen the legislative protection of tourism service trade. At present, the relevant laws and regulations of China's tourism industry include: Tourism Law of the People's Republic of China, regulations of travel agencies, relevant entry and exit regulations of China Customs, etc.

(2) Increase the support for inbound tourism

Under the background that all countries in the world attach great importance to the development of local tourism resources, Chinese government should strengthen the support to the inbound tourism. We will formulate a standardized and reasonable plan for tourism service trade, increase the construction of information infrastructure for tourism service trade, improve the e-commerce system for inbound tourism, promote the "in" to "out" transformation of tourism service trade, and reduce the tourism trade deficit between China and Thailand and the resulting adverse effects.

4 development prospect of China Thailand tourism service trade

China and Thailand are close in geographical location, friendly in history, frequent in contact, close in cooperation and convenient in transportation at present. In view of the different latitudes of the two countries, one is in the tropics, the other is across the tropical and temperate monsoon climate, and there must be different tourism resources, so the two countries have their own advantages and strong complementarities in tourism resources and location. Among the 10 ASEAN countries, Thailand is the first country to establish a strategic cooperative relationship with China. At present, with the further deepening of cooperation and ties between the two countries, the two sides actively integrate into the China ASEAN circle to achieve mutual benefit, seek development and promote harmony. The establishment of the AIIB can better shorten the distance between China and Thailand, infer the infrastructure construction of the two countries, and infer the tourism service trade relationship between China and Thailand in the future. Therefore, in the future, Thailand will continue to maintain its important position in China's inbound countries. In addition, in-depth consideration, the stability and prosperity of tourism service trade between the two countries can also promote the economic and trade ties between the two countries. Therefore, the two countries should strengthen the tourism service trade relations.

5 Conclusion

Through the analysis of inbound tourism between China and Thailand, we can realize that although the overall development trend of tourism service trade between China and Thailand is good, there are still some problems, such as "zero group fee" and the imbalance of tourism service trade between China and Thailand. Because of the limited capacity of the author, I will not list all the problems existing in the tourism service trade between the two countries, but the above two problems must be paid attention to by the two countries, and we should learn to prevent the situation from getting worse, so as to better promote the exchanges of Tourism service trade between the two countries. In view of the limitations of the data, the author is waiting for a more comprehensive and detailed analysis of the tourist groups of the two countries in the future. The research on tourism between the two countries will be more extensive and in-depth in the future. More standardized measures will be put forward and implemented, and the tourism service trade between China and Thailand will be booming.

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During her doctoral degree in Shanghai University, she worked as a designer and computer graphics in Shanghai. After graduating from School of Economics, Shanghai University. She opened a local tour guide company in Thailand and spent a gap year. Therefore, this study gets inspiration from the pain points at that time, hoping to benefit the relevant people of Thailand's tourism industry.

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